

Supplementary Information

Application of Rapeseed Meal Protein Isolate as a Supplement to Texture-Modified Food for the Elderly

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Figure S1. Rapeseed meal protein isolate from semi-pilot plant used in this study as an ingredient of texture-modified food.

Figure S2. Rapeseed meal protein isolate from full-pilot plant used in this study as an ingredient of texture-modified food.